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Keywords:

Sustainable polyurethane

Recycled BHET

PET marine litter

Glycolysis

Renewable macrodiol

Synthesis and characterization of sustainable polyurethanes from renewable and recycled feedstocks

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Abstract: In this paper, sustainable thermoplastic polyurethanes (TPU) were synthesized from a recycled bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate (BHET) monomer obtained by glycolysis of marine polyethylene terephthalate (PET) litter and from a renewable castor oil-derived macrodiol. The BHET was obtained in a closed reactor at 220 °C and a short time reaction of 30 minutes. The TPUs with different BHET contents, ranging from 10 to 30% by weight, incorporated as chain extenders, were synthesized in bulk without catalysts. In all polyurethanes, the content of the biobased macrodiol was at least 45 wt%. TPUs with commercial BHET have also been synthesized for comparative purposes. The BHET monomer produced and the TPUs synthesized were extensively characterized. The TPUs synthesized in this work, in which at least three quarters of their components are biobased and recycled, showed an interesting combination of thermal, thermomechanical and mechanical properties.

Keywords: sustainable polyurethane, recycled BHET, PET marine litter, glycolysis, renewable macrodiol

1. Introduction

The global production of plastics is estimated at around 300 million tons per year and continues to increase exponentially annually (Kumar Jha and Kannan, 2021). This results in a significant increase in end-of life plastics disposed of at landfills and in natural environments, such as the sea (Mwanza, 2021). Most of the plastic waste is landfilled due to the relatively low economic cost that implies, becoming a major problem for the expansion of plastic recycling (Kumar Jha and Kannan, 2021; Mwanza, 2021). However, in recent years the global environmental crisis has skyrocketed the need to be more efficient in the use of raw materials and resources.

This has led to the circular economy becoming increasingly relevant and the creation of policies focused on landfill reduction, driving a thriving path towards plastics recycling (Mwanza, 2021), and the development of sustainable polymers throughout their entire life cycle (Mohanty et al., 2022). Recycling polymers has several advantages such as oil preservation, minimization of greenhouse gas emissions, and energy savings (Al-Salem et al., 2009). According to the UN, progress in polymer recycling is also necessary, as outlined in Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12 related to consumption and production (United Nations, 2022).

Abundant plastic waste is a major environmental problem, since according to recent data it is estimated that each year 12.2 million tons of plastic end up in the sea (Plastics Recyclers Europe, 2020). The most common plastics found in the sea in proportion to their production are polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP) and poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) (Iñiguez et al., 2018; Peña-Rodríguez et al., 2021).

PET is a polyester that is manufactured by the polymerization of ethylene glycol and terephthalic acid during a polycondensation reaction (Li et al., 2016). In the last two decades poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) has been considered as one of the most important engineering polymers (Begley * et al., 2004; Ubeda et al., 2018), and nowadays this polyester is the main packaging material for mineral water, beverages and oils (Li et al., 2016). This material's good chemical and physical properties, such as good gas barrier properties, low density, great flexibility and its excellent mechanical and thermomechanical properties make it attractive for the packaging industry (Chapa-Martínez et al., 2016; Damayanti and Wu, 2021; Hu et al., 2005; Wei et al., 2017). For this reason, PET is one of the most widely produced plastics, and, due to poor management, once its useful life is over, a large percentage of it ends up in the sea.

Nowadays, the most common recycling system for PET plastics is mechanical recycling, due to its high profitability (Cornago et al., 2021). However, it is limited to recycling post-industrial and urban waste, since the degree of degradation of the material is low. Regarding marine PET litter, in addition to being a major environmental problem and requiring a much more complicated collection process, the material also presents a poorer quality, as it undergoes more severe degradation in the sea (Mendiburu-Valor et al., 2022). There are several factors that influence the degradation of plastics present in the sea, e.g., solar radiation, temperature or salinity of the sea, giving rise to different types of degradation, such as hydrolytic, thermo-oxidative or photodegradation (Iñiguez et al., 2018a; Peña-Rodríguez et al., 2021). For this reason, the techniques for recycling urban PET waste are not suitable for processing marine litter and it is of utmost importance to find another recycling route such as chemical recycling.

In a previous paper, a feasible chemical recycling route for marine PET bottles was successfully developed through glycolysis, obtaining high purity bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate (BHET) in a closed reactor at low reaction times (Mendiburu-Valor et al., 2021). Thus, the BHET monomer obtained can be used for the

synthesis of different polymers, from which a wide range of materials with very different properties can be obtained. For instance, it is possible to re-synthesize PET, as other authors have reported using BHET obtained from urban PET waste (Hu et al., 2020). However, it can also be the precursor of unsaturated polyesters, vinyl esters, epoxy resins and polyurethanes, among others (Abdelaal et al., 2011; Nikles and Farahat, 2005).

Polyurethanes (PUs) are characterized by their versatility and are one of the most widely produced polymers in the world, occupying seventh place in the Global production ranking with a production of 27 million tons per year (PlasticsEurope, 2021; Yuan et al., 2022). Due to the broad range of reactants available for their synthesis, materials with very different structures and a wide range of properties could be synthesized (Bergmeister et al., 2015; Munir et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2020). Moreover, it has been reported that polyurethanes can be chemically recycled back into their monomers or segments, or forming new ones, which can be subsequently employed for the synthesis of novel polymers (Gausas et al., 2021; Kiss et al., 2020; Kopczyńska et al., 2016; Simón et al., 2018).

In the literature, there are several papers in which polyurethanes are synthesized from BHET, either of commercial origin or produced from different waste via different procedures. In this context, Maafi et al. synthesized thermoplastic polyurethanes using commercial BHET and PCL as diols in different proportions, adding up to 20 wt% of BHET. They observed that the thermomechanical properties of PUs were improved due to the presence of aromatic rings of the BHET monomer (Maafi et al., 2010), becoming a potential raw material for PU synthesis. In recent years, recycled BHET from urban PET waste has been widely employed for the development of polyurethanes for several applications. For instance, Cevher and Sürdem synthesized crosslinked PU adhesives using BHET recycled from PET bottle waste by means of glycolysis reaction, castor oil and a commercial aromatic methylene diphenyl diisocyanate (MDI), in different ratios. The best adhesive performance was obtained for a formulation containing around 20 wt% of BHET and 40 wt% of castor oil (Cevher and Sürdem, 2021). Jamdar V. et al. synthesized an ecofriendly polyol based on linseed oil and BHET obtained from the recycling of urban PET waste through electron beam radiation, which subsequently reacted with various polyisocyanate crosslinkers for the preparation of good performance polyurethane thermoset coatings (Jamdar et al., 2017). Li Q. et al. synthesized waterborne polyurethanes using the BHET recycled from PET waste by alcoholysis as a chain extender, with remarkably improved mechanical properties, adhesion properties and thermal stability, and reduced water absorption (Li et al., 2022). PU rigid foams have been also synthesized using recycled PET. Li et al., synthesized PU foams using BHET recycled from PET textile waste by glycolysis and also using polymeric methylene diphenyl diisocyanate (pMDI) (Li et al., 2014). In another work, Ivdre et al., used the glycolyzed product of PET depolymerization to synthesize polyester with rapeseed oil for the production of polyurethane foams (Ivdre et al., 2018). On the other hand, in several studies,

Bhattacharyya et al., used BHET recycled from urban PET waste as a diol for the development of polyurethane-alginate nanoparticles (Bhattacharyya et al., 2017, 2016) and their blends for insulin encapsulation and delivery (Bhattacharyya et al., 2014). They employed aliphatic hexamethylene diisocyanates (HDI), which are considered less toxic than aromatic ones, as they avoid the formation of methylenedianiline (MDA), which has been shown to be hepatotoxic (Stripple et al., 2008).

However, despite intensive research on the incorporation of recycled BHET in the chemistry of polyurethanes, to the best of our knowledge, there are no research studies where BHET obtained from the chemical recycling of marine PET litter has been used to synthesize polyurethanes, or in thermoplastic, porous or compact thermosets, and even less so in polyurethanes with components also derived from renewable sources.

This paper focuses on the incorporation of recycled BHET from marine PET bottles and a macrodiol derived from castor oil into the formulation of segmented thermoplastic polyurethanes. They are constituted by two segments, the soft segment (SS) formed by a macrodiol and the hard segment (HS) formed by the reaction of a diisocyanate and a low-molecular-weight chain extender such as BHET. The new thermoplastic polyurethanes will be synthesized aiming at more than three quarters of their components being renewable and/or recycled. The objective of this study is to generate knowledge about the synthesis and properties of novel sustainable thermoplastic polyurethanes that contribute to promoting the circular economy.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

The PET bottles used in this study, were collected on the coast of the Basque Country, just between Deba and Zumaia in the flysch area (Gipuzkoa, Spain). For the glycolysis of PET samples, ethylene glycol (EG) was used as a solvent and chemically pure zinc acetate as a catalyst, both supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (USA). Glycolysis of PET was performed in a closed reactor with a PET:EG ratio of 1:3, under a pressure of 3 bars, at 220 °C and for a short reaction time of 30 min. The mixture obtained was filtered with excess water in order to recover the fraction rich in bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate and dried at 60 °C under vacuum, denoted from here on as BHET-m (Mendiburu-Valor et al., 2022). Commercial bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate (BHET-ref) from Sigma-Aldrich (USA) was used for comparative purposes. To carry out the synthesis of thermoplastic polyurethane, a macrodiol from renewable sources with 38% of renewable carbon content, Priplast 3192® (M_w 2000 g/mol) purchased from Croda (Snaith, UK), was used as the soft segment (SS). On the other hand, as an isocyanate for the hard segment (HS), hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI, Desmodur H) from Covestro (GE) was used.

2.2. Synthesis of polyurethane

Polyurethanes with different BHET-m contents were synthesized in bulk without any organic solvent or catalysts, in

order to follow green manufacturing guidelines. The synthesis was carried out following a two-step synthesis procedure in a 250 mL five-necked round-bottom flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer and dry nitrogen inlet. In the first step macrodiol and HDI were made to react at 110 °C for 2 h. In the second step the BHET was added to the mixture and stirred vigorously until a homogeneous mixture was obtained, which was poured between two Teflon-coated metal plates separated by 1.5 mm and pressed at 100 °C under 50 bar for 10 h. The NCO to OH group molar ratio was kept constant and equal to 1. Different polyurethanes varying the molar ratio of macrodiol:HDI:BHET-m were synthesized, as well as pure HS, HDI:BHET-m. As a reference, polyurethanes with BHET-ref (in the minimum and maximum molar ratios used with BHET-m) and pure HS, HDI:BHET-ref, were also synthesized. The chemical structure of the reactants used in the synthesis of thermoplastic polyurethanes are represented in the Figure S1. Table 1 summarizes the sample code, the molar ratio of components and hard segment and BHET content of the synthesized polyurethanes. The polyurethane samples obtained were stored in a desiccator for two weeks before their characterization. The appearance of the polyurethanes obtained can be seen in Figure 1.

Table 1. Sample code, molar ratio, hard segment (HS) and recycled BHET percentages of the synthesized polyurethane samples.

Sample code	Molar ratio	HS (%)	BHET (%)
	Macrodiol:HDI:BHET		
HDI:BHET-m	0:1:1	100	60
BHET-m 1:2:1	1:2:1	23	10
BHET-m 1:3:2	1:3:2	33	17
BHET-m 1:4:3	1:4:3	42	22
BHET-m 1:5:4	1:5:4	48	26
BHET-m 1:6:5	1:6:5	53	30
HDI:BHET-ref	0:1:1	100	60
BHET-ref 1:2:1	1:2:1	23	10
BHET-ref 1:6:5	1:6:5	53	30

2.3. Characterization

2.3.1. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The characteristic functional groups of BHET and of the synthesised polyurethanes, as well as hydrogen-bonding, were identified by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy using a Nicolet Nexus spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) equipped with a MKII Golden Gate accessory (Specac) and a diamond crystal at a nominal incidence angle of 45° and a ZnSe lens. The analyses were carried out in attenuated total reflection (ATR) mode in the 4000-650 cm⁻¹ wavenumber interval, conducting and 64 scans with a resolution of 8 cm⁻¹.

2.3.2 Nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR)

The nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR) spectra were recorded on an Avance Bruker 500 (Billerica, Massachusetts, USA) spectrometer equipped with a Z-axis gradient BBO probe. The ^1H NMR spectrum was recorded using sequence zg from Bruker's library at 500.13 MHz, a time domain of 64k, and a spectral width of 10000 Hz. The number of scans was 16, with a delay of 1 s and acquisition time of 3.2 s. All the samples were measured dissolved in DMSO-d₆.

2.3.3. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Thermal properties of BHET, macrodiol and synthesized polyurethane samples were determined by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, Columbus, Ohio, USA) using a Mettler Toledo DSC3+ device provided with a robotic arm and an electric intracooler as a refrigerator unit. 5–10 mg of sample was encapsulated in aluminium pans and heated from -90 to 240 °C at a heating rate of 20 °C min⁻¹ in nitrogen atmosphere. Thus, the glass transition temperatures (T_g), melting temperatures (T_m) and the enthalpies of fusion (ΔH_m) corresponding to neat components and polyurethane soft and hard segments were determined.

2.3.4. Gel permeation chromatography (GPC)

The weight and number average molar masses, M_w and M_n , respectively, of BHET-m and BHET-ref samples were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) using a Thermo Scientific chromatograph (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) equipped with an isocratic Dionex UltiMate 3000 pump and a RefractoMax 521 refractive index detector. The separation was carried out at 30 °C within four Phenogel GPC columns from Phenomenex with 5 μm particle size and porosities of 105, 103, 100, and 50 Å, located in an UltiMate 3000 thermostated column compartment. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was used as mobile phase at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. Samples were prepared solving the materials into THF at 1 wt.% and filtering with 2 μm pore size nylon filters. M_w and M_n were reported as weight average based on the calibration curve with monodisperse polystyrene standards. THF used in this technique was provided by Macron Fine Chemicals™ (Avantor, Gliwice, Poland).

2.3.5. Atomic force microscopy (AFM)

The morphology of the polyurethanes obtained using BHET from marine PET litter was analysed using a Bruker Dimension ICON scanning probe microscope equipped with a Nanoscope V controller. To that end, TESP-V2 type silicon tips with a nominal resonance frequency of 320 kHz and a cantilever spring constant of 42 N m⁻¹ were employed.

2.3.6. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

The thermal stability of BHET and synthesized polyurethanes was analysed by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, Columbus, Ohio, USA) using a TGA/SDTA851 Mettler Toledo device. Samples were heated from room temperature to 800 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ under nitrogen atmosphere.

2.3.7. Spectrophotometry

The colour parameters of synthesized TPU samples were measured using an X-rite 962 spectrophotometer (Grand Rapids, Michigan, USA). L^* (lightness-darkness), a^* (red-green), b^* (yellow-blue) parameters are given directly by the spectrophotometer and for a more accurate result, for each sample five tests have been carried out in the surface of the TPUs to obtain an average value. The TPU materials were placed on white standard to perform the measurement. The colour differences between samples and white standard (ΔE^*) as well as the whiteness index (WI) were calculated using the following equations:

$$\Delta E^* = \sqrt{(\Delta L^*)^2 + (\Delta a^*)^2 + (\Delta b^*)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$WI = 100 - \sqrt{(100 - L^*)^2 + a^{*2} + b^{*2}} \quad (2)$$

2.3.8. Water contact angle (WCA)

Static water contact angle (WCA) measurements were carried out at room temperature in order to analyse the surface hydrophilicity of synthesized TPU samples using a SEO Phoenix Series P-300 equipment (Kromtek Sdn Bhd, Selangor, Malaysia). A deionized water drop of 2 μL was deposited on the material's surface using a syringe of 0.4 mm diameter and the contact angle value formed by the drop of water was measured ten seconds after the droplet deposition. The average WCA value was obtained for each sample from the result of five water droplets deposited on the polyurethane plates prepared by compression moulding.

2.3.9. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

The dynamic mechanical behaviour of the polyurethanes was analysed by DMA in tensile mode on an Eplexor Gabo 100N analyser from Netzsch (Selb, Bavaria, Germany), using a static strain of 0.10%. The temperature was varied from -100 to 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a scanning rate of 2 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ and a fixed operation frequency of 10 Hz. Samples were cut into strips of 25 mm x 5 mm x 1.5 mm (length x width x thickness).

2.3.10. Mechanical properties

Mechanical testing was carried out at room temperature using an Instron 5697 device (Instron, Norwood, MA, USA) provided by a load cell of 500 N in tensile mode. Samples were cut with a length of 25 mm, width of 5 mm and thickness of 1.5 mm and tested at a crosshead speed of 20 mm min^{-1} with a distance between clamps of 16 mm. Young modulus (E), stress at yield (σ_y), stress at break (σ_b) and elongation at break (ϵ_b) were determined from stress-strain curves of five specimens of each series.

3. Results and Discussion

The fraction rich in BHET obtained from marine PET litter glycolysis, BHET-m, was compared with the commercial BHET-ref in order to determine its suitability as an alternative to the BHET-ref already used in the synthesis of polyurethanes, thus reducing the dependence on fossil raw materials and boosting the circular

economy. As can be observed in Figure S2a of the supporting information, both show a similar FTIR spectrum, denoting that both have the same characteristic functional groups. The characteristic stretching vibration of the hydroxyl group at 3442 cm^{-1} , the double band attributed to stretching vibration of ester carboxyl group at 1712 cm^{-1} and 1690 cm^{-1} and the absorption band of the aromatic group at 1508 cm^{-1} can be observed. Furthermore, their chemical structure was analysed by $^1\text{H NMR}$, Figure S2b, and both show the same spectrum. As can be observed, the peaks labelled in the BHET structure as 1, 2, 3 and 4, are assigned to the protons of the aromatic ring ($\delta\text{H} = 8.1\text{ ppm}$, s, 4H), the hydroxyl groups ($\delta\text{H} = 4.95\text{ ppm}$, t, 2H), methylene groups ($-\text{CH}_2-$) adjacent to the $-\text{OH}$ groups ($\delta\text{H} = 3.73\text{ ppm}$, m, 4H), and the methylene groups ($-\text{CH}_2-$) adjacent to the $-\text{COO}$ groups ($\delta\text{H} = 4.33\text{ ppm}$, t, 4H), respectively. The peak around 2.5 ppm corresponds to DMSO- d_6 used as a solvent and the peak at 3.3 can be attributed to residual H_2O (Imran et al., 2010; Lima et al., 2017). Regarding GPC (Figure S2c), two peaks can be observed for BHET-m, O2 ascribed to BHET dimer ($M_n = 380\text{-}393\text{ g mol}^{-1}$ and $M_w = 384\text{-}396\text{ g mol}^{-1}$ according to polystyrene standard) and O1 to the BHET monomer ($M_n = 168\text{-}176\text{ g mol}^{-1}$ and $M_w = 172\text{-}180\text{ g mol}^{-1}$), and three peaks for BHET-ref, O3 ascribed to BHET oligomer ($M_n = 591\text{-}649\text{ g mol}^{-1}$ and $M_w = 594\text{-}671\text{ g mol}^{-1}$) and the O2 and O1 ascribed to BHET dimer and monomer, respectively. Both BHETs are mainly constituted by the monomer, however in the case of BHET-ref there is a higher amount of dimer (11% O2 and 3% O2 for BHET-ref and BHET-m, respectively) and traces of oligomer (1% O3) are also observed. Regarding the thermal properties of both samples (Figure S2d), a prominent melting peak can be observed around $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ attributed to the BHET monomer. The biggest difference is that BHET-m showed a melting enthalpy centred at $213\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, whereas in the case of BHET-ref the endothermic peak is centred at a higher temperature ($278\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), suggesting the presence of crystalline structures formed by the BHET oligomers with greater chain length. This fact could also be related to what was observed in TGA (Figure S2e,f) where the BHET-ref showed a higher thermal stability. The first weight loss is related to the degradation of monomers and oligomers, whereas the second, centred at $433\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, is related to the degradation of PET formed during the thermogravimetric analysis (Chen, 2003). By comparing the thermal properties of both BHETs, it can be concluded that since the amount of dimer and oligomer is slightly higher in BHET-ref, it can form crystal structures with a higher melting temperature, close to the melting temperature of PET, which delays the onset of the degradation occurring at a slightly higher temperature.

In view of the results of structural and thermal analysis obtained, polyurethanes with different BHET-m content were synthesized, gradually increasing the BHET-m content, and were compared with polyurethanes synthesized with BHET-ref, specifically with the lower and the higher molar ratio used with BHET-m.

Firstly, the influence of the composition and the nature of the chain extender on the appearance of the TPU samples obtained was

analysed. As can be observed in Figure 1, showing a digital image of the TPUs prepared, regardless of the nature of the BHET, the opacity of the TPU increases as the hard segment content increases. Nevertheless, the TPUs with BHET derived from recycled PET are more brownish in colour, which is more intense as the BHET content increases in the TPU formulation. The influence of the increase of HS content on the opacity and colour of the samples was studied in more depth, analysing the colour parameters by spectrophotometry, Table 2. Regarding the L^* values related to lightness-darkness, a decrease is observed as the content of the hard segment increases, corroborating the tendency observed at a glance. Concerning the ΔE^* values in relation to colour changes, a gradual rise with increasing HS content is observed. However, these variations are more pronounced in the case of the polyurethanes synthesized with the BHET-m chain extender, probably due to their darker colour.

Figure 1. Digital image of the synthesized polyurethanes using BHET-m (top) and BHET-ref (down) as chain extender.

Table 2. Values of the different colour parameters for the TPU samples.

Sample	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE^*	WI
BHET-m 1:2:1	78.4	1.2	20.8	23.9	70.0
BHET-m 1:3:2	58.9	3.4	22.2	41.3	53.1
BHET-m 1:4:3	53.9	4.3	18.3	44.6	50.2
BHET-m 1:5:4	52.0	4.6	16.0	45.8	49.2
BHET-m 1:6:5	48.3	4.2	13.1	48.8	46.5
BHET-ref 1:2:1	85.1	0.1	10.4	12.3	81.8
BHET-ref 1:6:5	80.5	-2.4	1.7	15.5	80.3

The influence of the increase of hard segment content on the chemical structure of the resulting polyurethanes with BHET from marine litter was analysed by means of FTIR. Figure 2a shows the FTIR spectra of the synthesized polyurethanes, together with the biobased macrodiol and BHET-m used. As can be observed, none of the synthesized polyurethanes show the characteristic band of NCO groups centred at 2270 cm^{-1} , nor the O-H band stretching vibration observed in BHET-m at 3342 cm^{-1} , denoting that the polymerization was completed (Calvo-Correas et al., 2015; Hsieh and Chen, 2020; Maafi et al., 2010). All of them show a band centred at 3317 cm^{-1} ascribed to the N-H bond of the urethane group (Calvo-Correas et al., 2015; Tsai et al., 1998), which increases as the HS content increases, and thus, the number of urethane groups. As can be seen in the amide I region ($1750\text{-}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$) (Figure 2b), whereas the macrodiol shows a single band at 1727 cm^{-1} attributed to carbonyl groups (C=O), the polyurethanes present two bands. It is well known that in the case of polyurethanes, urethane C=O groups can be either free or hydrogen-bonded. Non-hydrogen-bonded (free) C=O groups can be observed around $1730\text{-}1718\text{ cm}^{-1}$, while

hydrogen-bonded C=O appear around 1700-1680 cm^{-1} (Calvo-Correas et al., 2017; Ryszkowska et al., 2010). In the case of the synthesized polyurethanes, the band at a higher wavenumber encompasses the C=O of the macrodiol as well as the urethane free C=O group. This band shifts slightly to a lower wavenumber, i.e. from 1727 to 1721 cm^{-1} , as HS content increases, according to the higher content of the urethane group in the polymer, whose intensity prevails over the intensity of the C=O groups of the macrodiol. Moreover, a band attributed to hydrogen-bonded C=O in the urethane group can be observed at 1689 cm^{-1} , which also increases with the HS content. Furthermore, all polyurethanes show a band in the amide II region (1600-1500 cm^{-1}) at 1535 cm^{-1} related to the bending vibration of N-H combined with the stretching vibration of C-N (Calvo-Correas et al., 2017; Datta and Głowińska, 2014). The intensity of this band increases as the HS increases, due to the greater contribution of urethane groups. The bands appearing between 1250 and 1110 cm^{-1} are related to the stretching vibration C-O-C (Pérez-Limiñana et al., 2005; Tang and Gao, 2017). Moreover, at 728 cm^{-1} we can observe the characteristic band related to C-H linkages in the aromatic groups (Bhattacharyya et al., 2017; Mendiburu-Valor et al., 2021). The intensity of the band increases when the HS content is higher, due the higher presence of BHET, which has an aromatic ring in its structure. In Figure 2c, the spectra of the polyurethanes synthesized with BHET-ref can be seen together with 1:6:5 polyurethane. Comparing both polyurethane systems, those with the lowest and highest molar ratio, it can be concluded that there is no relevant difference between the spectra of the polyurethanes derived from BHET-m and those derived from the commercial one.

Figure 2. a) FTIR spectra of the synthesized polyurethanes with BHET-m. b) Amide I region from 1800-1500 cm^{-1} . c) FTIR spectra of the synthesized polyurethanes with BHET-ref together with macrodiol and BHET-m 1:2:1 spectra.

Thermal properties of synthesized polyurethanes were analysed by DSC. The thermograms of the TPUs using BHET-m and, as a reference, the bio-based macrodiol and neat HS (HDI:BHET-m) employed are represented in Figure 3a. In addition, Table S1 summarizes the thermal transitions. The synthesized polyurethanes show several transitions associated to the macrodiol and neat HS. On the one side, a glass transition temperature around $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ can be observed, also observed in the macrodiol, which corresponds to the SS rich domain ($T_{g\text{SS}}$) and an endothermic peak, also seen in the macrodiol, associated with the melting enthalpy of the SS rich domain ($\Delta H_{m\text{SS}}$) centred at temperatures ranging from 12 to $23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. We can see that as HS content increases, the $T_{g\text{SS}}$ value remains almost constant, whereas $T_{m\text{SS}}$ and $\Delta H_{m\text{SS}}$ decrease according to the lower amount of crystallizable macrodiol. On the other hand, at higher temperatures, the glass transition observed in the neat HDI:BHET-m, ascribed to the HS rich domain ($T_{g\text{HS}}$) can be seen, as well as a second endothermic peak observed in neat HDI:BHET-m, which belongs to the melting enthalpy of the HS rich domain ($\Delta H_{m\text{HS}}$). As opposed to the abovementioned thermal behaviour of the SS rich domain, the $T_{g\text{HS}}$ and the $T_{m\text{HS}}$ and melting enthalpy of the HS rich domain increase as HS content increases. As mentioned above, this fact is related to the amount of crystallizable segment in the polyurethane formulation. That is, when polyurethanes contain a higher amount of crystallizable SS or HS, the probability of SS or HS chains to pack to form crystals is greater. This is due to the formation of longer chains, and therefore to the greater capacity for association through interurethane interactions (Corcuera et al., 2010). Thus, as HS content increases, the amount of macrodiol is lower, whereas the amount of diisocyanate and BHET is higher, hence, $T_{m\text{HS}}$ and $\Delta H_{m\text{HS}}$ increase, while $T_{m\text{SS}}$ and $\Delta H_{m\text{SS}}$ decrease. These results are in accordance with the increase of hydrogen-bonded C=O band observed in FTIR

spectra. Finally, the presence of differentiated transitions ascribed to HS and SS in the polyurethanes suggests a microphase-separated morphology.

Comparing the thermograms of the polyurethanes obtained from BHET-m with the ones using commercial BHET (Figure 3b) no significant differences are observed, denoting that the material's thermal properties are not compromised when a BHET recycled from marine PET litter is employed in the formulation of polyurethanes.

Figure 3. a) DSC thermograms of polyurethanes synthesized with BHET-m, neat macrodiol and HDI:BHET-m segment. b) DSC thermograms of polyurethanes synthesized with BHET-ref, neat macrodiol and HDI:BHET-ref segment.

In the same way, dynamic mechanical behaviour of polyurethane samples synthesized with the recycled BHET-m was also analysed. In Figure 4, the temperature dependence of storage modulus (E') and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) are represented. The $T_{g,SS}$ and $T_{m,HS}$ results obtained from DMA are summarized in Table S1 together with the values of DSC study. At low temperature, all synthesized polyurethanes show similar storage modulus and in all cases a drop of around $-52\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is observed, being more pronounced for the samples with higher SS content. On the other hand, the $\tan \delta$ peak shows a maximum in the same temperature interval which is related to the glass transition temperature of the SS domain ($T_{g,SS}$) (Calvo-Correas et al., 2017, 2015; Datta and Głowińska, 2014). The magnitude of this peak decreases as the HS content increases, since the height of the $\tan \delta$ peak is related to the amount of amorphous material, which is higher for the samples with major SS content (Crawford et al., 1998). At higher temperatures, the storage modulus curve reaches a quasi-plateau in all samples, related to the interconnectivity of HS domains. Higher storage modulus values are observed in this interval as the HS content of the polyurethane increases in agreement with the DSC results (Table S1). Moreover, this plateau extends to higher temperatures as the HS content of the samples increases, providing higher thermomechanical stability to the polyurethane samples, and starts to decrease with the onset of the melting of previously observed crystals. The same behaviour is observed for the samples synthesized from BHET-ref, Figure 3b.

Figure 4. Storage modulus (E') and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) of the synthesized polyurethanes: a) with BHET-m and b) with BHET-ref.

The morphology of synthesized polyurethanes using BHET-m was analysed by AFM (Figure 5). As can be observed, different domains can be distinguished in the polyurethanes, denoting that the synthesized TPUs have a phase-separated microstructure. The darker regions are ascribed to amorphous domains, whereas the lighter ones are attributed to the crystalline ones. The frequency and size of the lighter areas increases as the HS content increases, suggesting that the addition of BHET increases the ability of chains to pack forming interurethane interactions in agreement with DSC results, leading to larger crystalline domains being obtained.

Figure 5. Phase AFM images of TPUs synthesized from BHET-m with 1:2:1, 1:4:3 and 1:6:5 molar ratios (scale bar 200 nm).

Thermal stability of the polyurethanes synthesized, as well as neat components, was analysed by TGA. The thermograms and their corresponding derivatives are represented in Figure 6. As can be observed, the degradation profiles change as HS content increases, being more appreciable in the derivative (Figure 6b). All TPU samples show a degradation step centred at 420 °C, also observed in the macrodiol, related to the breakage of ester bonds in the SS macrodiol (Bueno-Ferrer et al., 2012; Corcuera et al., 2011). In polyurethanes with a high HS content, i.e. 1:6:5 and 1:5:4, the

degradation peak observed at 316 °C in neat HS related to the degradation of the urethane group is clearly observed. As the HS content decreases, the intensity of that peak decreases and shifts to higher temperatures, becoming a shoulder for the polyurethanes with the lower HS content. This shift at higher temperatures, which results in an overlap with the macrodiol degradation peak, is attributed to a greater dispersion of the small- size hard segments in the macrodiol-rich phase, as has already been observed by AFM. In addition, a third degradation step related to the degradation of the residue formed was observed at a higher temperature (Mondal and Hu, 2007), which is more noticeable as HS content increases (Figure 6a), in line with the trend observed for neat HS. Comparing the thermal degradation behaviour of the polyurethanes synthesized using BHET-m with those obtained using BHET-ref in Figure 6c and d, similar behaviour is observed, denoting that the origin of the BHET employed does not interfere in the degradation profile of the polyurethane.

Figure 6. a) TG and b) DTG curves of polyurethanes synthesized with BHET-m and neat HDI:BHET-m and macrodiol. c) TG and d) DTG curves

of polyurethanes synthesized with BHET-ref and neat HDI:BHET-ref and macrodiol.

Mechanical behaviour of the synthesized polyurethanes was also analysed by performing tensile tests. The average values of tensile modulus, stress at yield, stress at break and elongation at break for BHET-m and BHET-ref systems are summarized in Table 3 and the plotted tensile tests are shown in Figure S3.

As the HS content increases, higher tensile modulus, stress at yield and stress at break values are obtained, due to the fact that, as mentioned above, the crystallizable HS domains act as reinforcement for the soft matrix (Auad et al., 2010). However, the increase of HS content decreases the strain at breakage, according to the higher crystallinity of the material that could act as breaking and stress concentration points. It can be deduced that increasing the HS content makes the material more rigid, due to the higher crystallinity as observed by DSC and due to the aromatic ring of the BHET monomer. TPUs synthesized using BHET from the chemical recycling of marine PET bottles show similar properties to TPUs synthesized with commercial BHET used as a reference, thus corroborating that they are a suitable alternative to raw materials from fossil sources. Moreover, the synthesized polyurethanes showed properties in the range of those obtained for polyurethanes synthesized using polycaprolactone diol as soft segment and commercial BHET and HDI as hard segment (Maafi et al., 2011, 2010). However, by comparing them with polyurethanes synthesized with aliphatic chain extenders like 1,4-butanediol or 1,3-propanediol, and aliphatic or aromatic diisocyanates, in general, stiffer polyurethanes with higher modulus are obtained due to the aromatic structure of BHET (Fernández-d'Arlas et al., 2010; Ugarte et al., 2014).

Table 3. Young modulus, strain at break, stress at yield and stress at break values of the synthesized polyurethanes.

Sample	E (MPa)	ϵ_b (%)	σ_y (MPa)	σ_b (MPa)
BHET-m 1:2:1	28 ± 3	176 ± 29	0.7 ± 0.2	4.1 ± 0.2
BHET-m 1:3:2	40 ± 2	184 ± 13	1.3 ± 0.3	5.6 ± 0.3
BHET-m 1:4:3	66 ± 3	89 ± 5	1.5 ± 0.0	7.0 ± 0.2
BHET-m 1:5:4	82 ± 3	45 ± 5	1.6 ± 0.2	6.9 ± 0.5
BHET-m 1:6:5	107 ± 1	45 ± 1	1.6 ± 0.3	8.4 ± 0.1
BHET-ref 1:2:1	29 ± 3	182 ± 22	0.9 ± 0.1	4.2 ± 0.2
BHET-ref 1:6:5	143 ± 11	16 ± 3	2.4 ± 0.2	7.8 ± 0.4

Finally, the water contact angle of the synthesized polyurethanes was measured. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. WCA results of the synthesized polyurethanes.

	Water contact angle (°)				
	1:2:1	1:3:2	1:4:3	1:5:4	1:6:5
BHET-m	79 ± 4	75 ± 4	75 ± 1	79 ± 1	79 ± 3

BHET-ref	79 ± 1	-	-	-	80 ± 1
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It is observed that water contact angle it is independent to HS content increase, since there are no significant changes. On the one hand, the increase of HS content results in an increase in dipole-forming urethane groups, which should lead to a decrease in WCA (Fernández-D'Arlas et al., 2015; Fernández-D'Arlas et al., 2008). However, at the same time, the amount of BHET-m increases, which has hydrophobic aromatic groups in its structure as can be observed in Figure S1 of the supporting information (Sarkar et al., 2014). Therefore, since two counteracting effects are taking place no variation in WCA is observed.

4. Conclusions

In this study, sustainable thermoplastic polyurethanes were successfully synthesized using chemically recycled BHET from marine litter PET bottles and a macrodiol derived from renewable sources. In this way, polyurethane formulations containing up to 30% recycled BHET were obtained. In all cases, the renewable and/or recycled content is more than half.

It was observed that the increase of recycled BHET leads to obtaining materials with high thermomechanical stability, since the segments made up of aromatic BHET and HDI isocyanate are capable of forming interurethane interactions between adjacent chain segments, resulting in crystalline structures with high melting temperatures. Moreover, these structures, dispersed in the macrodiol matrix, act as reinforcement and provide stiffness to the material. The increase of the hard segment content results in stiffer and less ductile materials. Furthermore, the physical-chemical, thermal and mechanical properties of the TPUs synthesized from recycled BHET are comparable to those of polyurethanes synthesized from fossil-derived commercial BHET, since both BHETs showed similar features.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the use of recycled BHET from marine litter as a chain extender for the production of segmented thermoplastic polyurethane is a suitable alternative to recover highly degraded PET residues. In addition, using biobased components such as macrodiols derived from renewable vegetable oils, polyurethanes with a high content of recycled and/or renewable components can be synthesized. Green synthesis strategies can also be followed, without using organic solvents or catalysts. All this contributes to the development of sustainable polyurethanes in line with the circular economy model.

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References

- Abdelaal, M.Y., Sobahi, T.R., Makki, M.S.I., 2011. Chemical transformation of pet waste through glycolysis. *Constr Build Mater* 25, 3267–3271.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2011.03.013>
- Al-Salem, S.M., Lettieri, P., Baeyens, J., 2009. Recycling and recovery routes of plastic solid waste (PSW): A review. *Waste Management*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2009.06.004>
- Auad, M.L., Mosiewicki, M.A., Richardson, T., Aranguren, M.I., Marcovich, N.E., 2010. Nanocomposites made from cellulose nanocrystals and tailored segmented polyurethanes. *J Appl Polym Sci* 115, 1215–1225.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/app.31218>
- Begley *, T.H., Biles, J.E., Cunningham, C., Piringer, O., 2004. Migration of a UV stabilizer from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) into food simulants. *Food Addit Contam* 21, 1007–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02652030400010447>
- Bergmeister, H., Seyidova, N., Schreiber, C., Strobl, M., Grasl, C., Walter, I., Messner, B., Baudis, S., Fröhlich, S., Marchetti-Deschmann, M., Griesser, M., di Franco, M., Krssak, M., Liska, R., Schima, H., 2015. Biodegradable, thermoplastic polyurethane grafts for small diameter vascular replacements. *Acta Biomater* 11, 104–113.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2014.09.003>
- Bhattacharyya, A., Mukherjee, D., Mishra, R., Kundu, P.P., 2017. Preparation of polyurethane–alginate/chitosan core shell nanoparticles for the purpose of oral insulin delivery. *Eur Polym J* 92, 294–313.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2017.05.015>
- Bhattacharyya, A., Mukherjee, D., Mishra, R., Kundu, P.P., 2016. Development of pH sensitive polyurethane–alginate nanoparticles for safe and efficient oral insulin delivery in animal models. *RSC Adv* 6, 41835–41846.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/C6RA06749B>
- Bhattacharyya, A., Mukhopadhyay, P., Kundu, P.P., 2014. Synthesis of a novel pH-sensitive polyurethane-alginate blend with poly(ethylene terephthalate) waste for the oral delivery of protein. *J Appl Polym Sci* 131, 40650.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/app.40650>
- Bueno-Ferrer, C., Hablot, E., Garrigós, M. del C., Bocchini, S., Averous, L., Jiménez, A., 2012. Relationship between morphology, properties and degradation parameters of novative biobased thermoplastic polyurethanes obtained from dimer fatty acids. *Polym Degrad Stab* 97, 1964–1969.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2012.03.002>
- Calvo-Correas, T., Santamaria-Echart, A., Saralegi, A., Martin, L., Valea, Á., Corcuera, M.A., Eceiza, A., 2015. Thermally-responsive biopolyurethanes from a biobased

- diisocyanate. *Eur Polym J* 70, 173–185.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EURPOLYMJ.2015.07.022>
- Calvo-Correas, T., Ugarte, L., Trzebiatowska, P.J., Sanzberro, R., Datta, J., Corcuera, M.Á., Eceiza, A., 2017. Thermoplastic polyurethanes with glycolysate intermediates from polyurethane waste recycling. *Polym Degrad Stab* 144, 411–419.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.POLYMDEGRADSTAB.2017.09.001>
- Cevher, D., Sürdem, S., 2021. Polyurethane adhesive based on polyol monomers BHET and BHETA depolymerised from PET waste. *Int J Adhes Adhes* 105, 102799.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijadhadh.2020.102799>
- Chapa-Martínez, C.A., Hinojosa-Reyes, L., Hernández-Ramírez, A., Ruiz-Ruiz, E., Maya-Treviño, L., Guzmán-Mar, J.L., 2016. An evaluation of the migration of antimony from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) plastic used for bottled drinking water. *Science of The Total Environment* 565, 511–518.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2016.04.184>
- Chen, C.-H., 2003. Study of glycolysis of poly(ethylene terephthalate) recycled from postconsumer soft-drink bottles. III. Further investigation. *J Appl Polym Sci* 87, 2004–2010. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.11694>
- Corcuera, M.A., Rueda, L., Fernandez d’Arlas, B., Arbelaiz, A., Marieta, C., Mondragon, I., Eceiza, A., 2010. Microstructure and properties of polyurethanes derived from castor oil. *Polym Degrad Stab* 95, 2175–2184.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2010.03.001>
- Corcuera, M.A., Rueda, L., Saralegui, A., Martín, Ma.D., Fernández-d’Arlas, B., Mondragon, I., Eceiza, A., 2011. Effect of diisocyanate structure on the properties and microstructure of polyurethanes based on polyols derived from renewable resources. *J Appl Polym Sci* 122, 3677–3685. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.34781>
- Cornago, S., Rovelli, D., Brondi, C., Crippa, M., Morico, B., Ballarino, A., Dotelli, G., 2021. Stochastic consequential Life Cycle Assessment of technology substitution in the case of a novel PET chemical recycling technology. *J Clean Prod* 311, 127406.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2021.127406>
- Crawford, D.M., Bass, R.G., Haas, T.W., 1998. Strain effects on thermal transitions and mechanical properties of thermoplastic polyurethane elastomers. *Thermochim Acta* 323, 53–63. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6031\(98\)00541-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6031(98)00541-3)
- Damayanti, Wu, H.-S., 2021. Strategic Possibility Routes of Recycled PET. *Polymers (Basel)* 13, 1475. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13091475>
- Datta, J., Głowińska, E., 2014. Effect of hydroxylated soybean oil and bio-based propanediol on the structure and thermal properties of synthesized bio-polyurethanes. *Ind Crops Prod* 61, 84–91.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.INDCROP.2014.06.050>
- Fernández-d’Arlas, B., Rueda, L., Fernández, R., Khan, U., Coleman, J.N., Mondragon, I., Eceiza, A., 2010. Inverting polyurethanes synthesis: effects on nano/micro-structure and mechanical properties. *Soft Mater* 9, 79–93.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1539445X.2010.525173>

- Fernández-D'Arlas, B., Alonso-Varona, A., Palomares, T., Corcuera, M.A., Eceiza, A., 2015. Studies on the morphology, properties and biocompatibility of aliphatic diisocyanate-polycarbonate polyurethanes. *Polym Degrad Stab* 122, 153–160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2015.10.023>
- Fernández-D'Arlas, B., Rueda, L., de La Caba, K., Mondragon, I., Eceiza, A., 2008. Microdomain composition and properties differences of biodegradable polyurethanes based on MDI and HDI. *Polym Eng Sci* 48, 519–529. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pen.20983>
- Gausas, L., Kristensen, S.K., Sun, H., Ahrens, A., Donslund, B.S., Lindhardt, A.T., Skrydstrup, T., 2021. Catalytic hydrogenation of polyurethanes to base chemicals: from model systems to commercial and end-of-life polyurethane materials. *JACS Au* 1, 517–524. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacsau.1c00050>
- Hsieh, C.-C., Chen, Y.-C., 2020. Synthesis of bio-based polyurethane foam modified with rosin using an environmentally-friendly process. *J Clean Prod* 276, 124203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124203>
- Hu, Y., Wang, Y., Zhang, X., Qian, J., Xing, X., Wang, X., 2020. Synthesis of poly(ethylene terephthalate) based on glycolysis of waste PET fiber. *Journal of Macromolecular Science, Part A* 57, 430–438. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10601325.2019.1709498>
- Hu, Y.S., Prattipati, V., Mehta, S., Schiraldi, D.A., Hiltner, A., Baer, E., 2005. Improving gas barrier of PET by blending with aromatic polyamides. *Polymer (Guildf)* 46, 2685–2698. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.POLYMER.2005.01.056>
- Imran, M., Kim, B.K., Han, M., Cho, B.G., Kim, D.H., 2010. Sub- and supercritical glycolysis of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) into the monomer bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate (BHET). *Polym Degrad Stab* 95, 1686–1693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.POLYMDEGRADSTAB.2010.05.026>
- Iñiguez, M.E., Conesa, J.A., Fullana, A., 2018a. Recyclability of four types of plastics exposed to UV irradiation in a marine environment. *Waste Management* 79, 339–345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2018.08.006>
- Iñiguez, M.E., Conesa, J.A., Soler, A., 2018b. Effect of marine ambient in the production of pollutants from the pyrolysis and combustion of a mixture of plastic materials. *Mar Pollut Bull* 130, 249–257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARPOLBUL.2018.03.040>
- Ivdre, A., Fridrihsone-Girone, A., Abolins, A., Cabulis, U., 2018. Effect of different concentration of rapeseed oil and recycled poly (ethylene terephthalate) in polyols for rigid polyurethane foams. *Journal of Cellular Plastics* 54, 161–177. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021955X16670585>
- Jamdar, V., Kathalewar, M., Dubey, K.A., Sabnis, A., 2017. Recycling of PET wastes using Electron beam radiations and preparation of polyurethane coatings using recycled material. *Prog Org Coat* 107, 54–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.porgcoat.2017.02.007>
- Kiss, G., Rusu, G., Peter, F., Tănase, I., Bandur, G., 2020. Recovery of flexible polyurethane foam waste for efficient reuse in industrial formulations. *Polymers (Basel)* 12, 1533. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym12071533>

- Kopczyńska, P., Calvo-Correas, T., Eceiza, A., Datta, J., 2016. Synthesis and characterisation of polyurethane elastomers with semi-products obtained from polyurethane recycling. *Eur Polym J* 85, 26–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2016.09.063>
- Kumar Jha, K., Kannan, T.T.M., 2021. Recycling of plastic waste into fuel by pyrolysis - a review. *Mater Today Proc* 37, 3718–3720. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.10.181>
- Li, B., Wang, Z.-W., Lin, Q.-B., Hu, C.-Y., 2016. Study of the migration of stabilizer and plasticizer from polyethylene terephthalate into food simulants. *J Chromatogr Sci* 54, 939–951. <https://doi.org/10.1093/chromsci/bmw025>
- Li, M., Luo, J., Huang, Y., Li, X., Yu, T., Ge, M., 2014. Recycling of waste poly(ethylene terephthalate) into flame-retardant rigid polyurethane foams. *J Appl Polym Sci* 131, 40857. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.40857>
- Li, Q., He, H., Zhang, C., Liang, X., Shen, Y., 2022. Research on synthesis of polyurethane based on a new chain extender obtained from waste polyethylene terephthalate. *J Appl Polym Sci* 139, 52402. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.52402>
- Lima, G.R., Monteiro, W.F., Ligabue, R., Santana, R.M.C., 2017. Titanate nanotubes as new nanostructured catalyst for depolymerization of PET by glycolysis reaction. *Materials Research* 20, 588–595. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-5373-mr-2017-0645>
- Maafi, E.M., Malek, F., Tighzert, L., 2010. Synthesis and characterization of new polyurethane based on polycaprolactone. *J Appl Polym Sci* 115, 3651–3658. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.31448>
- Maafi, E.M., Tighzert, L., Malek, F., 2011. Synthesis and characterization of new polyurethanes: influence of monomer composition. *Polymer Bulletin* 66, 391–406. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00289-010-0347-1>
- Mendiburu-Valor, E., Mondragon, G., González, N., Kortaberria, G., Eceiza, A., Peña-Rodríguez, C., 2021. Improving the efficiency for the production of bis-(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate (BHET) from the glycolysis reaction of poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) in a pressure reactor. *Polymers (Basel)* 13, 1461. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13091461>
- Mendiburu-Valor, E., Mondragon, G., González, N., Kortaberria, G., Martin, L., Eceiza, A., Peña-Rodríguez, C., 2022. Valorization of urban and marine PET waste by optimized chemical recycling. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 184, 106413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2022.106413>
- Mohanty, A.K., Wu, F., Mincheva, R., Hakkarainen, M., Raquez, J.-M., Mielewski, D.F., Narayan, R., Netravali, A.N., Misra, M., 2022. Sustainable polymers. *Nature Reviews Methods Primers* 2, 46. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-022-00124-8>
- Mondal, S., Hu, J.L., 2007. Influence of hard segment on thermal degradation of thermoplastic segmented polyurethane for textile coating application. *Polym Plast Technol Eng* 46, 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03602550600948715>

- Munir, M.A., Badri, K.H., Heng, L.Y., Inayatullah, A., Badrul, H.A., Emelda, E., Dwinta, E., Kusumawardani, N., Wulandari, A.S., Aprilia, V., Supriyono, R.B.Y., 2022. Design and synthesis of conducting polymer bio-based polyurethane produced from palm kernel oil. *Int J Polym Sci* 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/6815187>
- Mwanza, B.G., 2021. Introduction to Recycling, in: *Recent Developments in Plastic Recycling*. Springer. pp. 1–13. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-3627-1_1
- Nikles, D.E., Farahat, M.S., 2005. New motivation for the depolymerization products derived from poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) waste: a review. *Macromol Mater Eng* 290, 13–30. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mame.200400186>
- Peña-Rodríguez, C., Mondragon, G., Mendoza, A., Mendiburu-Valor, E., Eceiza, A., Kortaberria, G., 2021. Recycling of marine plastic debris, in: *Recent Developments in Plastic Recycling*. Springer. pp. 121–141. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-3627-1_6
- Pérez-Limiñana, M.A., Arán-Aís, F., Torró-Palau, A.M., Orgilés-Barceló, A.C., Martín-Martínez, J.M., 2005. Characterization of waterborne polyurethane adhesives containing different amounts of ionic groups. *Int J Adhes Adhes* 25, 507–517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijadhadh.2005.02.002>
- Plastics Recyclers Europe, 2020. Marine Litter [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.plasticsrecyclers.eu/marine-litter> (accessed 5.9.20).
- PlasticsEurope, 2021. Plastics—the Facts 2021 [WWW Document]. URL <https://plasticseurope.org/knowledge-hub/plastics-the-facts-2021/> (accessed 6.10.22).
- Ryszkowska, J.L., Auguścik, M., Sheikh, A., Boccaccini, A.R., 2010. Biodegradable polyurethane composite scaffolds containing Bioglass® for bone tissue engineering. *Compos Sci Technol* 70, 1894–1908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COMPSCITECH.2010.05.011>
- Sarkar, K., Rama, S., Meka, K., Bagchi, A., Krishna, N.S., Ramachandra, S.G., Madras, G., Chatterjee, K., 2014. Polyester derived from recycled poly(ethylene terephthalate) waste for regenerative medicine †. *Royal Society of Chemistry* 58805–58815. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ra09560j>
- Simón, D., Borreguero, A.M., de Lucas, A., Rodríguez, J.F., 2018. Recycling of polyurethanes from laboratory to industry, a journey towards the sustainability. *Waste Management* 76, 147–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2018.03.041>
- Stripple, H., Westman, R., Holm, D., 2008. Development and environmental improvements of plastics for hydrophilic catheters in medical care: an environmental evaluation. *J Clean Prod* 16, 1764–1776. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2007.12.006>
- Tang, Q., Gao, K., 2017. Structure analysis of polyether-based thermoplastic polyurethane elastomers by FTIR, 1H NMR and 13C NMR. *International Journal of Polymer Analysis and Characterization* 22, 569–574. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1023666X.2017.1312754>

- Tsai, Y.-M., Yu, T.-L., Tseng, Y.-H., 1998. Physical properties of crosslinked polyurethane. *Polym Int* 47, 445–450. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0126\(199812\)47:4<445::AID-PI82>3.0.CO;2-B](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0126(199812)47:4<445::AID-PI82>3.0.CO;2-B)
- Ubeda, S., Aznar, M., Nerín, C., 2018. Determination of oligomers in virgin and recycled polyethylene terephthalate (PET) samples by UPLC-MS-QTOF. *Anal Bioanal Chem* 410, 2377–2384. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-018-0902-4>
- Ugarte, L., Fernández-d’Arlas, B., Valea, A., González, M.L., Corcuera, M.A., Eceiza, A., 2014. Morphology-properties relationship in high-renewable content polyurethanes. *Polym Eng Sci* 54, 2282–2291. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pen.23777>
- United Nations, 2022. Sustainable Development Goals [WWW Document]. URL <https://sdgs.un.org/goals#goals> (accessed 7.5.22).
- Wang, B., Ma, S., Xu, X., Li, Q., Yu, T., Wang, S., Yan, S., Liu, Y., Zhu, J., 2020. High-performance, biobased, degradable polyurethane thermoset and its application in readily recyclable carbon fiber composites. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* 8, 11162–11170. https://doi.org/10.1021/ACSSUSCHEMENG.0C02330/SUPPL_FILE/SCOC02330_SI_001.PDF
- Wei, H. sen, Liu, K.T., Chang, Y.C., Chan, C.H., Lee, C.C., Kuo, C.C., 2017. Superior mechanical properties of hybrid organic-inorganic superhydrophilic thin film on plastic substrate. *Surf Coat Technol* 320, 377–382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SURFCOAT.2016.12.025>
- Yuan, Z., Nag, R., Cummins, E., 2022. Ranking of potential hazards from microplastics polymers in the marine environment. *J Hazard Mater* 429, 128399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.128399>